

LCANIAN PSYCHOANALYSIS OF MOTHER-CHILD RELATIONSHIP IN TONI MORRISON'S BELOVED

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ABSTRACT

Toni Morrison's *Beloved* digs deep into the history of slavery in America. It blurts out the chronicle of tragedies that came upon the enslaved people in the country. It depicts how the slaves were made to bear the lives of subordinate creatures. It illustrates how they were snatched off their basic and necessary possessions. It delineates the fact of the black people's being born slaves and their giving birth to slaves. Nevertheless, there are the unmitigated longings to embrace freedom even at the expense of one's survival. If not for those who have served their whole life in subjugation, at least for those who are to come to this world for the first time are there intangible and tangible attempts for liberty. This is what Sethe, the mother of Beloved has in her mind for her children. She would move heaven and earth only to be able to liberate her children from the venomous shackles of slavery which she has been born into and has been serving all through her life. She has in her mind to go for the most hapless option if it is needed to set her children free from the worst curse in human history. This is where Sethe loses her daughter, her Beloved only to feel the utmost motherly demand that lets her decipher the inseparability of mother-child bond. This universally-felt-fact can be rationally elucidated through Jaques Lacan's Psychoanalysis that traces how a child feels for its mother and vice-versa. This article aims to interpret the relationship between Sethe and Beloved through Lacanian psychoanalytic principles. It also targets to come up with some logical conclusions on how Lacan's psychoanalytic criticism can be put into use to comprehend the novel, *Beloved*, in its maximum extent. It is perceptible that this attempt and its outcome will hopefully pave the way for some more empirical research to the literary scholars concentrating on Toni Morrison.

Keywords: Jacques Lacan, Psychoanalysis, Mother, Daughter, Relationship, *Beolved*

INTRODUCTION

Toni Morrison's epoch making novel, *Beloved* has the story regarding a slave mother who slaughters her own daughter for the noble motto of salvaging her from the chronic clasp of slavery. As a matter of fact, Sethe, the mother has in mind to kill all her children only for the infallible purpose of liberating them from the dehumanizing servitude. But, at least, she succeeds in setting one free and letting her enter the universe which is free from all sorts of shame and

disgrace emerging from human discrimination. The 'School teacher' (Morrison, 42), the sadist slave torturer gets compelled to retire from exploiting his nefariously sadistic approach on Sethe and her children when he observes what has already been done to get rid of his inhumanly woven chains of servitude. Sethe and her children are let be alone in the 124 where this infanticide takes place in the way Jesus sacrifices for the salvation of humanity. The mother, Sethe is to live here forgetting her past and nurturing her present that requires her to count every moment to beacon her Beloved to come back to her so that she can effectuate her long repressed love that has been kept preserved for the slain daughter. Sethe and her youngest daughter, Denver, continue living in this house. They know that there is another person in this house and she is Beloved, with all her presence and movement. Sethe never ceases to believe that one day Beloved will show up and there will be huge sharing of love between the mother and the daughter. This auspicious day comes into reality. Beloved shows up and proclaims her love for her mother. The mother and the daughter talk,

Tell me the truth. Didn't you come from the other side?

Yes, I was on the other side

You came back because of me?

Yes.

You rememory me?

Yes, I remember you

You never forgot me?

Your face is mine.

Do you forgive me?

Will you stay?

You safe here now. (Morrison, 1988, pg. 215)

The mother cries again to let Beloved know how intently she has been awaiting her,

I waited for you

You are mine

You are mine

You are mine. (Morrison, 1988, pg. 217)

French psychoanalyst Jacques Lacan (1901-1981) considers this mother-child urging to be inevitable and it has greater significance in language and the formation of the unconscious (Tyson, 2006). Tyson (2006) also brings to the front that Lacanian psychoanalysis champions that the mother-child relationship regards itself to be so strong and inseparable that the mother demands none if she has her child and the latter needs none if it has its mother.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Mayfield (2002) presents that Sethe as a young slave girl neither knows her parents nor whether they are alive or dead somewhere. She only knows that her mother used to work as a slave and sees vividly that her daughters are also going to live as slaves for the rest of their lives. She does not have the slightest shortage of love that might let her allow this to happen. She feels she must free her children from the venomous shame of bondage. She has her infinite motherly love to take into action any attempt if it requires to save her children. If by killing she can liberate her children, she won't refrain. Sethe's feeling resonates in the hearts of all child-loving people. In fact, this takes place in her owing to the lingering experience of servitude and inhumanity exercised on the slaves. The ins and outs of her psychological tenets have been dilapidated by the indescribable tortures she has seen being executed on her kinds. Her mind cannot take it anymore, not for herself let alone her beloved children. Osagie (1994) states that Toni Morrison employs psychoanalytic instruments to exhume the forgotten past of the slave voyages and touches intently the closeness people possess in the numerous coils of time. Morrison's narrative craftsmanship decisively creates a vivid illustration of the psychic demonstrations of American slavery. It also acts like a well-devised psychoanalysis that establishes a link between the imaginal and the real (Osagie, 1994). Toni Morrison's *Beloved*, deals primarily with the sacred and irreparable love that has its abode between mother and child. In fact, the novel depicts lucidly what a mother can do for her love towards children and what she suffers when there prevails the absence of her beloved ones. In order to be able to feel one's existence and importance in the world, one has to feel loved and felt which is why one needs someone to render feelings that help one feel alive (Godek, 2013). Morrison brings to light the phenomenon that attaches the mother to the baby and baby to the mother. This explains a lot why Sethe surrenders herself to all the wishes and demands of Beloved only to afford to be felt and recognized (Godek, 2013). Losing her baby daughter, Sethe has only one way to survive in this mundane world, and that is to earnestly continue looking forward to meeting her lost child albeit in the form of an apparition. To Sethe, Beloved is a second chance that enables her to give the utmost try to prove and implement her love for her daughter (Larrick, 2007). Beloved's presence signifies to Sethe the coming back of her slain daughter for whom she has preserved all of her motherly love and longing for years (Larrick, 2007). Thus are the phenomena of mother-child kinship in the novel. Toni Morrison's *Beloved* stands out to be a novel that deals passionately

with the themes of mothering and motherhood (Mayfield, 2002). Moreover, if a mother who has gone through the cruelest treatment of slavery gets snatched off her only abode of happiness, she undergoes the worst kind of sorrow, which is why Sethe commits the most horrible deed only to retain her soul's urging. *Beloved* talks about a slave mother who envisions her children to be free from the shackles of slavery (Mayfield, 2002). She loses but saves her child. In *Beloved*, Toni Morrison delineates the traumatic detachment of a black slave mother from her daughter (Ramirez, 2014). Here begins Sethe's excruciating agony. The unmerciful torture that haunts Sethe, the bereaved mother, has its clasp effects on her psyche and brings to the world the unspeakable pangs a mother goes through for being detached from her child (Ramirez, 2014). This mother-child bond, its detachment, subsequent pangs of suffering and the later futile hankering to reunite can be analyzed vividly through the psychoanalysis posited by Jacques Lacan (1901-198), the French psychoanalyst.

Lacanian Psychoanalysis Relating to Mother-Child

Jaques Lacan explains that a child contains itself to be an inseparable part of its mother (Tyson, 2006). With the mother, the child feels that it is in a tie of reciprocal contentment. It feels, "My mother is all I need and I am all my mother needs" (Tyson, 2006). This belief has its effectuation every now and then from the child's part on the mother. As a result, the mother-child and the child-mother relationships emerge to be the tightest one and make all other phenomena in the world look very passive and peripheral. Lacan describes it to be "The mother's desire for the child and the child's desire for the mother" (Tyson, 2006). Though Lacanian Psychoanalysis mainly deals with how a child acquires language and what really happens in the ways of a child to acquire the language, it sheds quite a comprehensive light on the unique union between the child and its mother. Any sort of separation of the child from its mother, even if it is linguistic, turns to be irreparable and haunts both the child and the mother incessantly. This detachment, to Lacan, is 'an experience of loss' (Tyson, 2006) that both of them hanker after regaining or compensating for. But this loss is never retrieved no matter what they succeed in achieving. Lacan calls this lost object of desire, 'object petit a' or 'small object' (Tyson, 2006). This term actually refers very intently to something that is uniquely personal, individual and so extremely private (Tyson, 2006). This has the expository implication that articulates the object of desire 'belongs to me and therefore influences only me' (Tyson, 2006).

As the long-awaiting mother, Sethe cries out loud, "BELOVED, she my daughter. She mine....." (Morrison, 1988, pg. 200). To Lacan, all the longings of the mother are for her children and all those of the children are for their mother. This signifies an absolute feeling of possessiveness that exists between a mother and her child. Sethe emphasizes again, "When I tell you you mine, I also mean I'm yours. I wouldn't draw breath without my children" (Morrison, 1988, pg. 203). In *Beloved*, Morrison portrays a surprising mother-child orientation that stands out exclusively analogous to what Jaques Lacan has established in his psychoanalytic theory. This linking is somewhat unconsciously knitted in the mutual formation of the individual and it is as lucid as a language (Das, 2012). This psychological possessiveness does not endure any slightest

separation from each other. Sethe does never want to be disintegrated from her little daughter, Beloved. She wants to keep her with herself at least dead if not alive. Then she continues suffering the pangs of loss and never stops awaiting her child. When Beloved re-appears, Sethe has all the reasons to be grateful, “She come back to me , my daughter, and she is mine” (Morrison, 1988,pg. 204).

As for Beloved, she speaks of her heart,

I AM BELOVED and she is mine. I see her take flowers away from leaves she puts them in a round basket the leaves are not for her she fills the basket she opens the grass I would help her but the clouds are in the way how can say things that are pictures I cannot separate from her there is no place where I stop her face is my own and I want to be in the place where her face is and to be looking at it too a hot thing. (Morrison, 1988, pg. 210).

Separation and loss

Tyson (2006) states in the description of Lacanian psychoanalysis that a child experiences the biggest separation when it gets detached from the intimate union with its mother during its immersion in the ‘Imaginary Order’. According to Lacan, this separation symbolizes the child’s most crucial experiences of loss that it struggles to compensate for all-through its life, but to no purpose (Tyson, 2006). The separation between Sethe and Beloved means losing each other’s best thing. Therefore, it is irreparable and unlivable without for each other. Due to a commotion devised by the community, Beloved leaves 124, the house where Sethe and Denver have been living and which has been haunted by her. Losing Beloved, Sethe retires to bed. Paul D comes to be beside her and asks if she is ok. Sethe mourns that ‘her best thing has left her’ (Morrison, 1988, pg. 272). Though Lacan’s psychoanalysis is all about the language acquisition of a child instigated by separation from its mother, it, as a matter of fact, tells a lot more about the literal disintegration between mother and children. The moment a child gets isolated psychologically from the inborn union of oneness, it starts doing things to fulfill the loss and retain the lost completeness (Tyson, 2006).

The Ever-Existing Attempt to Retain the Mother-Child Bond

Lacan (1901-1981) says that once separated, the child continues struggling all-through its life to make for the lost affinity with the mother (Tyson, 2006). Through multiple different objects and issues of the material world, both the mother and the child go on striving to get reunited no matter even if the attempt turns to be the most illogical one (Tyson, 2006). In *Beloved*, happens the same sort of phenomenon. Beloved, the slain daughter of Sethe comes to her mother after a long time when she is a grown-up, albeit as a ghostly being. The mother is overjoyed to get her

child back. She does not mind whether the baby is an apparition or a true human being. Her long inflicted soul is soothed and she is grateful.

Sethe exalts in happiness. She cries,

You are back. You are back.

Will you smile at me?

Can't you see. I'm smiling?

I love your face. (Morrison, 1988, pg. 215)

Sethe does not bother about the fact that the girl she calls Beloved is, in fact, a phantom, and it takes advantage of the incommensurable love of the desperate mother. She continues responding to and fulfilling the weird and unrefined wishes of Beloved only to be able to have the companion of her lost daughter.

CONCLUSION

Although Lacan's psychoanalysis elucidates the process a child acquires its mother tongue, he unwittingly proposes a convincing foundation of the inseparable bond between mother and her children. As long as the child is integrated with the mother, it does not feel any want, and neither does the mother. But, for any reason, if there occurs a disintegration between the mother and the child, neither of them feels alive in this mortal world. Such is the case in Toni Morrison's *Beloved*. In the first place, Sethe commits the horrible sin that is for the greater sake of her child. Subsequently, she goes on suffering the worst agony for the absence of her child. Consequently, she continues awaiting the impossible arrival of the slain child. It can be because of the dire intensity of the hankering in the mother's forlorn heart that the apparition of the lynched child whom she calls Beloved arrives. Through this ever-touching mother-child story, Toni Morrison reverberates the happenings in the time of the abominable slavery in America and elsewhere. After all, the incorporation of the narrative of Morrison and the psychoanalysis of Lacan renders some substantial scopes for seeing deep into the texture of mother-child relationship now and hereafter.

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